

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437930>Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF OUTCOMES OF SUBLAY VERSUS
ONLAY MESH REPAIR****¹Dr. Muhammad Hamza Sohail, ²Dr. Muhammad Asif, ³Dr. Muhammad Abu Bakar**
¹Hamdard College of Medicine and Dentistry, Hamdard University, Karachi.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:****Objective:** The objective of this study is to compare Sublay and Onlay mesh repair techniques, results in ventral hernias.**Study Design:** Prospective-study**Place and Duration of Study:** This study was conducted at the Surgical Department of Hamdard University Hospital, Karachi from March 2017 to February 2018.**Materials and Methods:** The study included 200 patients who underwent incisional hernia, including both sexes, male and female (140 female and 60 male), Paraumbilical and epigastric hernia. The surgical complications such as wound infection, recurrence and seroma formation were compared between both Onlay Mesh repair and sublay.**Results:** Seroma formation occurrence was 14 percent, wound infection was found in 10% patients, 2% recurrence and mesh removal were 2%.**Conclusion:** We found Sublay mesh repair surgery to be superior as compared to Onlay because it presented with lesser complications in ventral abdominal wall hernia patients.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Muhammad Hamza Sohail,**

Hamdard College of Medicine and Dentistry, Hamdard University, Karachi.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Hamza Sohail et al, A Comparative Study Of Outcomes Of Sublay Versus Onlay Mesh Repair., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08(1).

INTRODUCTION:

Ventral hernias are ordinarily experienced in our surgical practice after inguinal hernias. These emerge from the anterior abdominal wall and fixed through various strategies which require exhaustive information on anatomy of anterior abdominal wall. Of every abdominal hernia, the basic is incisional hernia. The frequency of incisional hernia is 2-20%. The different variables causing this hernia are inappropriate abdominal injury closer, twisted contamination and wound dehiscence. No proof is identified with etiology of incisional hernia with respect to the abdominal injury closer with synthetic monofilament biodegradable sutures versus closer with non-absorbable sutures. Cross over/slanted incisions have demonstrated lower pace of incisional hernias as analyzed vertical incisions. [1]

The ventral hernia is fixed by three strategies viz onlay, sublay and trim.

These strategies utilize the implantation of prosthetic lattice in various layers of anterior abdominal wall. [2] The prosthetic cross section can be put between the subcutaneous tissues of the abdominal wall and anterior rectus sheath (Onlay network fix) just as in the preperitoneal plane made between the rectus sheath (Sublay network repair). But the best situation for the embeddings the lattice has not been definitively settled till date according to literature. [3]

Fix of hernia absconds by network was presented in the late 1980. The preperitoneal (Sublay) network was first portrayed by Renestope, Jean Rives and George Wantz. This procedure is viewed as the best one for the open fix of the abdominal ventral hernias. [4,5,6]

The Onlay is stitched over the essential fix to the anterior rectus sheath as fortification yet this maintenance stitch line under strain and the lattice expands the contamination rate. The Sublay network fix is the most favored strategy by the specialists on the planet now a days on account of its least disease rate and can be performed by open and laparoscopic methods.[7,8] Inlay network fix is hard to perform laparoscopically so it is generally done by open methodology. More over cross section is in direct contact with digestive system so it can deliver deadly complexity like fecal fistula. [9,10]

The reasoning of our examination is to discover the better strategy for open ventral hernia network fix by contrasting the consequences of Sublay versus Onlay methods to assist the patients in our locale.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The planned study was completed in 200 patients. This study was led in surgical division, Hamdard University Hospital, Karachi from March 2018 to February 2019. All the patients were conceded from Surgical outpatient division (OPD). They were explored biochemically and imaging was done. Cardiovascular and anesthesia wellness was obtained and patients were moved to Operation Theater on elective rundown.

Patients were performed a sublay mesh repair or Onlay mesh repair. Surgical methods of Sublay and Onlay mesh repair were done under anesthesia. All aseptic measures were finished during a medical procedure. Broad spectrum anti-microbial was injected during the enlistment of anesthesia.

In Sublay mesh repair a medical procedure was begun by eliminating the old surgical scar in instances of incisional hernias however in Para umbilical hernias, cross over incision was made, while in epigastric hernias vertical incision was made. Fastidious dismemberment was done to uncover the imperfection. Hernia sac was uncovered. Basic visceral injury was kept away from via cautious analyzation. Around the imperfection the bed for mesh was framed about in any event 4-5 cm. Polypropylene mesh was put under the deformity in retro muscular layer. The mesh moored to the peritoneum by various lines.

Attractions drains were put for incisional hernia and huge Paraumbilical hernia >4 cm just for 3-4 days. In Onlay mesh repair a medical procedure was begun as same as Sublay mesh repair. The edges of the deformity were approximated by polypropylene stitch material than mesh was set over the sheath of muscle and moored. Redivac drains were set. Wound was shut and dressed.

RESULTS:

In our study, of complete 200 patients there were 140 females and 60 males. The female and male patient's proportion was 2.33:1. Patients included were aged between 30-60 years. Mean age was 45 years. Patients having essential incisional hernia were 138. Patients of Paraumbilical hernia were 44 while 18 of epigastric hernia.

In instances of incisional hernias, the past medical procedures were as following, bowel related 60, gynecological related 70, biliary related 30, appendectomy related 20 and renal related medical procedures 20. In our study it was seen that injury contamination was regular and most basic reason for

incisional hernia formation. In 120 instances of the incisional hernia, the 80 cases have defected 8-10 cm, 30 cases 5-8 while 10 cases have under 5cm.

Concerning post-operative confusions, the seroma formation was the most widely recognized. 24 cases in Onlay mesh repair and 4 cases in Sublay mesh repair created seroma formation. 18 cases in Onlay

meshrepair and 2 cases in Sublay mesh repair created wound disease. Mesh expulsion was done in 2 cases in Onlay mesh repair while none was in Sublay mesh repair. Reoccurrence was 2 cases in Onlay mesh repair while none was in Sublay mesh repair. Fold rot was 2 cases in Onlay mesh repair while none was in Sublay mesh repair.

Table No. 1: Age and sex distribution

Age (years)	Male	Female	Total	Percent
30-40	12	30	42	21%
41-50	30	70	100	50%
51-60	18	40	58	29%

Table No. 2: Previous operations for patients with incisional hernia

Type of surgery	Number	Percent
Bowel related	60	30%
Gynaecological Related	70	35%
Biliary related	30	15%
Appendectomy Related	20	10%
Renal related	20	10%
Total	200	100%

Table No. 4: Post-operative complications

Post-operative Complications	Onlay mesh repair	Sublay mesh Repair
Seroma	24	4
Wound infection	18	2
Mesh removal	2	0
Recurrence	2	0
Flap necrosis	2	0
Total	48 (24%)	6 (3%)

DISCUSSION:

In surgical practice, the mesh repair of ventral hernias is a challengeable errand. Different surgical systems have been utilized to repair and reinforce the hernia

defect by mesh.11In our study, Sublay mesh repair has demonstrated to be the better one when contrasted with Onlay. Sublay mesh repair has brought down the reoccurrence rate, wound

contamination and different inconveniences and has given good result results. Reoccurrence, mesh expulsion and fold rot were zero in instances of Sublay procedure. In previous studies, the operative time was more in Sublay mesh repair when contrasted with the Onlay mesh repair as a result of shaping preperitoneal space however in our study it was by and large different.¹² The base time was had the chance to play out the strategy by moving toward the space through various ways.

Seroma formation is a typical and incessant early inconvenience in past investigations and it is less in Sublay mesh repair. In our study it is additionally seen that seroma formation is low discovered uniquely in 4 (2%) patients as contrasted and Onlay mesh repair in which it was available in 24 (12%) patients.^{13,14,15,}

Wound disease is around 6-12% in past examinations; while in our study it is 9% in Onlay and just 1% in Sublay procedure^{16, 17.} Past examinations show that position of strain free mesh is acceptable strategy with bring down the reoccurrence rate.^{18,19}In our study, it is additionally seen that pressure free mesh has diminished reoccurrence. In Onlay it is discovered distinctly in 2 (1%) patients while in Sublay it is 0%. In one study, it is discovered that fold rot is discovered after Sublay strategy however in our study none of the patient accompanied whine of fold corruption on development.

In different investigations, the most widely recognized patients accompanied incisional hernias were recently worked for significant bowel surgeries^{20,21} however for our situation it is unique and amazing that patients with gynecological issues were conceded and worked for incisional hernias.

The rate of ventral hernias is regularly found in ladies when contrasted with male in our study like other studies²² and the Paraumbilical hernia is the second toward the end in rate after incisional hernia.

CONCLUSION:

Our study concludes that Sublay mesh repair is the superior procedure in all types of ventral hernias as compared to Onlay mesh repair. In this study we compared studies from around the world with our study and they all suggest that Sublay repair is better with lower complication rates and offers rapid recovery.

Conflict of Interest: The study has no conflict of interest to declare by any author.

REFERENCES:

1. Stoppa RE .The treatment of complicated groin and incisional hernias. *World J Surg* 1989;13:545-54.
2. Ahmed I, Mahmood D, Khan J. Use of Mesh in the management of recurrent incisional hernias. *Pak J Surg* 1995;11:101-2.8.
3. Mahabhleshwar B, Santosh S.Preperitoneal mesh repair of incisional hernia. *Ind J Surg* 2007;69; 95-98.
4. Iqbal CW, Pham TH, Joseph A. Long term outcome of 254 complex incisional hernia repair using modified Rives-Stoppa technique *World J Surg* 2007;31:2398-2404.
5. Marten-Duce A, Noguerles F, Villet AR. Modifications to Rives technique for midline incisional hernia repair. *Hernia* 2001;5:70-72
6. Langer C, Schaper A, Liersch T. Prognosis factors in incisional hernia surgery: 25 years of experience. *Hernia* 2005;9:16-21
7. Mahabhleshwar B, Santosh S. Preperitoneal mesh repair of incisional hernia. *Ind J Surg* 2007;69; 95-98.
8. Berry MF, Paisley S, Low DW. Repair of large complex recurrent incisional hernias with retromuscular mesh and panniculectomy *Am JS Surg* 2007;194:199-204.
9. Ibrahim AH, El-Gammal AS, Heikal MM. Study between ‘onlay’ and ‘sublay’ hernioplasty in the treatment of uncomplicated ventral incisional hernia. *Menoufia Med J* 2015;28:11-6.
10. Goda El-Santawy HM, El-Sisy AA, El-Gammal AS, El-Kased AF, Sultan HM. Evaluation of retromuscular mesh repair technique for treatment of ventral incisional hernia. *Menoufia Med J* 2014; 27:226-9.
11. Oh T, Hollands MJ, Langcake ME, Parasyn AD. Incisional hernia repair: a Retrospective review and early experience of laparoscopic repair. *Surg* 2004; 74:50-56
12. Aoda FS, Ibrahim AS.Sublay versus onlay mesh repair of ventral hernia. *QMJ* 2013;9(16):208-213.
13. Ali Q. Murad F, Awan TA, Khan A, Malik AZ. Onlay Versus Sublay Technique of Repairing Ventral Abdominal Hernia. *JRMC* 2013;17(2): 192-194.
14. Martel G, Ahmad J, Taylo N. Treatment of refractory seroma after incisional hernia repair. *Gut* 2013;62:a19-a20.
15. Haytham MA, Hur K, Hirter A, Kim LT. Seroma in ventral incisional herniorrhaphy: incidence, predictocors and outcome. *Am J Surg* 2009; 198:639-644.
16. Jat MA, Memon MR, Rind GH, Shah SQA.

- Comparative evaluation of “Sublay” versus “Inlay” meshplasty in incisional and ventral hernias. *Pak J Surg* 2011;27(1):54-58.
17. Saeed N, Iqbal SA, Shaikh BA, Baqai F. Comparison between onlay and sublay methods of mesh repair of incisional hernia. *J Post Med Inst* 2014;28 (4):400-3.
 18. Leithy M, Loulah M, Greida HA, Baker FA, Hayes AM. Subaly hernioplasty versus onalyhernioplasty in incisional hernia in diabetic patients. *Menoufia Med J* 2014; 27:353-8.
 19. Milad NM, Said SM, Samir M. Comparison between onlay and retromuscular drainless mesh repair for para-umbilical hernia with divarication of recti. *Kasr El Aini J Surg* 2009; 10:11-6.
 20. Kharde K, Dogra BB, Panchabhai S, Rana KV, Sridharan S, Kalyan SA. comparative study of onlay and retrorectus mesh placement in incisional hernia repair. *Med J DY Patil Univ* 2013; 6:258-62.
 21. Elsesy A, Balba MA, Badr M, Latif MA. Retromuscular preperitoneal versus traditional onlay mesh repair in treatment of incisional hernia. *Menoufiya Med J* 2008; 21:209-20.
 22. Gleysteen JJ. Mesh-reinforced ventral hernia repair: Preference for 2 techniques. *Arch Surg* 2009; 144:740-5.